

DEVELOPMENT PROCESSES OF INVESTMENT COMPETENCE IN NAMANGAN REGION DURING THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE.

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Annotation: In this article, the attraction of foreign investments in Namangan region during the years of independence, indicators of growth are covered, achievements and problems are discussed. In Namangan region, as well as in the entire republic, an effort was made to highlight the importance of creating a positive investment environment.

Key words: investment, capital, foreign, population, investor.

In the development of the country, it is important to have a well-formed investment environment, to attract foreign investors, as well as local investors, to the economy and production processes. The word investiture is derived from Latin and means to fight¹. In order to develop the country's economy, investments can be made from the country's budget or on the basis of foreign investments, in the form of money, securities, land, and buildings. There are types of it, such as foreign investment and private investment, from the state budget and financial sources.

One of the priority tasks of the state policy is to rapidly develop the investment environment and protect the legal interests of investors in the development of the country's economy. Therefore, the development of Uzbekistan's economic relations with foreign countries, its further strengthening, and the promotion of the country's economic opportunities abroad, its international prestige, the expansion and acceleration of attracting investments, is a priority task in the economic system². For this, it is necessary to create legal bases for the development of this field. In Uzbekistan, since 1996, the government of the republic has annually adopted a specific development program from the state budget and extra-budgetary funds, foreign investments and loans. For the development of this industry, a number of legal documents have been created, among which we can include the laws "On Investment Activities", "On Foreign Investments and Guarantees of Activities of Foreign Investors", and "On Foreign

¹ [O'zNE](#). The first volume. Tashkent, 2000

² Sh. Mirziyoev. We will build a free and prosperous, democratic country of Uzbekistan together. "Uzbekistan". T.: 2016. 24B

Investments"³. With the help of these legal frameworks, a favorable investment climate was formed.

By 2005, the volume of capital investments in Namangan region amounted to 108,806.7 million soums, the increase compared to 2004 was 105.4 percent⁴. A large part of these funds was directed to the development of construction works. In 2006, the amount of capital invested amounted to 141.3 billion soums⁵. By 2011, the amount of work in this field reached 663.2 billion soums⁶. By this year, the export revenue of Namangan region was 82.8 million dollars, and the import revenue was equal to 123 million USA dollars⁷. This year, foreign funds in the amount of 17.33 million USA dollars were allocated in the field of investment in the region⁸. The increased investments were spent on works such as construction, drinking water supply, gas supply. Currently, there are 57 joint ventures with foreign investment in the region, 7 of which have temporarily stopped their activities. The volume of production of these enterprises was 296,584 million soums, the volume of export was 29,500 USA dollars, and the import was 62,520 dollars⁹.

By the time of the new Uzbekistan, more and more attention was paid to the investment sector. A lot of work was done to eliminate problems and shortcomings in the field. In 2017, the amount of investment in fixed capital in Namangan region amounted to 3051.9 billion soums¹⁰. 3.8% of this amount comes from the budget of the Republic, 3.7% from the State Special Fund, 42.2% from the funds of enterprises and residents, 14.4% from commercial bank loans and other loans, 35.7% from foreign investments and loans. and 0.2% was formed from the children's sports development fund¹¹.

In 2021, 245 trillion soums were transferred from the total sources of financing for the development of economic and social sectors in the Republic of Uzbekistan. In dollar equivalent, 23.1 billion USA were dollarized, and the increase compared to 2020 was 105.1%. In recent years, measures have been taken to create a favorable investment climate in the Republic, to attract foreign investments, especially foreign investments. As a result, 30,149.2 billion soums of direct foreign investment were invested in the Republic in 2021, equal to

³ Lex.uz

⁴ Archive of Namangan region. 948-1-506. 5b

⁵ Static yearbook of regions of Uzbekistan 2006. 152B

⁶ Statistics Committee. Macroeconomics. Statistical program. 5B

⁷ Statistics Committee. Macroeconomics. Statistical program. 7B

⁸ Data provided by the Statistics Agency.

⁹ The current archive of the Namangan regional government.

¹⁰ Main economic indicators of Namangan region. 2017 Namstat.uz

¹¹ Investment climate of Uzbekistan. 2017 Stat.uz

12.3% of the total invested funds. Investment works in Namangan region amounted to 13302.4 billion USA dollars, of which 7.6% came from the budget of the Republic, 25.1% from enterprise and population funds, 16.2% from the population, 32.6% from foreign investments and loans, 1, 4% water supply and sewage system development fund, 0.5%; recovery and development fund, 16.6% was formed from commercial bank loans and other debt funds¹². A large part of these funds was spent on new construction works, as well as expansion, reconstruction, and modernization works.

Along with the achievements, a number of shortcomings and flaws are highlighted in the direction of investment. In particular, according to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 29, 2010 "On the investment program of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2011"¹³, within the framework of 3 projects, 60.7 million dollars of foreign investments and loans will be absorbed this year, and in practice, by the end of the year, only 16.5 million dollars (annual plan 27.2%) amount of foreign investments and loans were absorbed. Including: 20.0 million dollars this year under the project "Conducting geological exploration works in the Namangan-Tergachi and Chust-Pop investment network in the Fergana Valley of the Republic of Uzbekistan". it is planned to attract foreign direct investments. But on November 8, 2011, the technical committee of the KNOC company found it uneconomical to continue geological exploration in Namangan-Tergachi and Chust-Pop investment blocks and decided to suspend all work.

On 28-29 of 2011, at the technical seminar held at the International Business Center, as a result of the negotiations with the specialists of Uzbekneftegaz, KNOC specialists reconsidered their opinion on the prospect of the Chust-Pop network and withdrew from the idea of suspending the work. Therefore, due to unforeseen delays, the Operator was unable to start excavation works within the specified time limits, and the foreign investment of 20.0 million dollars scheduled for 2011 was actually withdrawn. 16.47 million dollars. (82.4%) foreign investments are only absorbed.

This year under the project "Implementation of the investment project on development and pre-exploration of the Mingbulok mine".

It was planned to attract foreign investments in the amount of 29.2 million dollars, but by the end of the year no investment was attracted at all. Also,

¹² State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Socio-economic situation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2021. Tashkent. 2022y. 130b

¹³ Lex.uz

according to the report of the Republic Coordination Council No. 02-02/1-190 dated December 31, 2011, this project was removed from the Address List of the 2011 Intestion Program. Foreign investment in the amount of 11.5 million dollars is planned to be attracted this year in the production project of kalava yarn in the foreign enterprise "Hain Teks" in Namangan. According to the schedule approved for the project in 2011

It is planned to attract foreign investment in the amount of 11.5 million dollars. However, foreign investments were not attracted at the end of the year due to the lack of financial opportunities of foreign investors¹⁴.

In 2016, in the Kashkadarya, Namangan and Surkhondarya regions of the Republic, there were 18 projects involving foreign investment, and an average of 3 million dollars was attracted for each project, and this situation is not surprising.

In conclusion, it can be said that investment, foreign investments are one of the main factors accelerating the economic development of any country. Therefore, the development of this field is an urgent issue, and as a result, new jobs will appear in any branch of the economy, and it will allow people working in these fields to have permanent sources of income. At the same time, investments have a positive effect on the social life of the population, in particular, a part of foreign investments is spent on improving gas and water supply, construction and reconstruction works.

Literature:

1. O'zME. The first volume. Tashkent, 2000
2. Sh. Mirziyoev. We will build a free and prosperous, democratic country of Uzbekistan together. "Uzbekistan". T.: 2016. 24B
3. Lex.uz
4. Archive of Namangan region. 948-1-506. 5b
5. Static yearbook of regions of Uzbekistan 2006. 152B
6. Statistics Committee. Macroeconomics. Statistical program. 5B
7. Statistics Committee. Macroeconomics. Statistical program. 7B
8. Data provided by the Statistics Agency.
9. The current archive of the Namangan regional government.
10. Main economic indicators of Namangan region. 2017 Namstat.uz
11. Investment climate of Uzbekistan. 2017 Stat.uz

¹⁴ Information obtained from the current archives of the Namangan regional government.

12. State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Socio-economic situation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2021. Tashkent. 2022y. 130b
13. Lex.uz

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